

The Sphinx: Golden and Plastic

Solving one of history's oldest riddles.

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Abstract

The Great Sphinx at Giza is arguably the oldest, most famous and recognisable fixed statue on Earth. The consensus is that it started as a monolith or yardang, before being carved and later renovated to that of a feline with a human head. The Sphinx is oddly proportioned and positioned relative to the rest of the Giza plateau, with the distinction of facing directly due east. Its position is however not random, but mathematically determined using both the Golden and Plastic ratios. These two constants have unique arithmetic and geometric properties. The Sphinx's location and dimensions lead to several references to π and other favoured irrationals, continuing a theme prevalent in the rest of the Giza site plan. This raises questions about who built it, and when.

Keywords: Giza, Great Sphinx, History of Mathematics

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1 Introduction

There are three natural outcrops incorporated into features at Giza. Both the Khufu and Khafre pyramids are built over hillocks, saving the builders some effort. The third outcrop is the Sphinx.

The Sphinx seems disconnected from the existing pyramids, standing off to the side, facing due East to watch the rising sun and moon.

Appearances are deceiving. Everything in the original Giza site was designed, and that includes the Sphinx. Far from being a randomly placed, modified natural feature, the Sphinx is actually part of the Giza site plan.

This paper shows how the Sphinx locks itself into the site plan, as developed in earlier papers.

The calculations shown in Appendix A often refer to π , which is very much the designer's signature. The greater double-square site design was inspired by the stars, and I find it hard to accept that the builders were lucky enough to find three outcrops in exactly the right spots to build Khufu, Khafre, and the Sphinx. The only alternative I can see is that those outcrops are man-made, by removing everything around them. That makes the whole Giza project even more extensive and impressive than we thought.

1.1 Version history

- 1.0.0 31 December 2025 First version.

1.2 Symbols and values

Giza is a construction site, so we are doing engineering, not pure mathematics, and thus $1.999 = 2.0$.

We will be using integer fractions to approximate various irrational constants, which by definition cannot be expressed as simple fractions. We can, however, approximate them to various levels of accuracy with fractions. Well-known examples are π approximated as $\frac{22}{7}$, $\frac{333}{106}$, or $\frac{355}{113}$, and $\sqrt{2}$ approximated as $\frac{99}{70}$.

Table 1 shows important numbers and their values typically used at Giza.

Symbol	Name	“Full” value	Typical Giza values
\mathbb{G}	(Royal) cubit	0.5236 m	0.5236 m
π	Archimedes' constant	3.141592653...	3.14 or 3.142 or 3.1416 or 3.14159
$\frac{\pi}{2}$	Half π	1.570796326...	1.57 or 1.571 or 1.5708
e	Euler's number	2.718281828...	2.72 or 2.718 or 2.7183
φ	Golden ratio	1.618033988...	1.62 or 1.618 $\varphi + 1 = \varphi^2 = 2.618$ or 2.62
ρ	Plastic ratio	1.324717957...	1.3247 $\rho + 1 = \rho^3 = 2.3247$
$\sqrt{2}$	Root 2	1.414213562...	1.414 or 1.4142
$\sqrt{3}$	Root 3	1.732050807...	1.732
$\sqrt{5}$	Root 5	2.236067977...	2.236
c	Speed of light	299 792 458 m/s	299.79 Mm/s
		572 560 080.2 \mathbb{G} /s	572.56 MG/s (currently)
		572 553 297.6 \mathbb{G} /s	572.55 MG/s (in 55.5k BCE)
α	Fine Structure Constant	0.0072973525...	0.0073 or 0.007297
α^{-1}	Inverse FSC	137.03599908...	137

Table 1: Symbols, names and values

Our eyes are very sensitive to decimals, influenced by our education. We may see 3.14 or 3.142 or 3.1416 as π , but do we as easily see 1.62, or numbers that round to that, as φ ? Similarly, do we automatically see 2.72, or numbers that round to that, as e ? Again, this is engineering, not pure mathematics.

I use “cubit” for the royal cubit \mathbb{G} . The short or common cubit is not used at Giza.

We will be dealing in lengths, and it is worth noting that 0.1 \mathcal{C} is about 5 cm, which is not much on distances of over 100 metres.

Our research indicates that Giza was built long before the dynastic Egyptians, and that the builders used a digital cubit, not one divided into digits, hands, palms, etc. This is more precise for measuring by eye than our current metric system, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Centimetres and millimetres compared to decimal centicubit and millicubit divisions.

The reader might also ponder how exactly one measures long distances over uneven ground. A top end laser measuring device for the construction industry [1] offers a range of 250 metres, or 477 \mathcal{C} , with accuracy of $\pm 0.01\%$. However the distance from the north end of Khufu to the south end of Menkaure is 1732 \mathcal{C} . How do you measure that accurately? High-end hunting or golf range-finders [2], [3] can measure up to almost 3 km, but at much reduced accuracy, typically $\pm 0.5\%$ or worse above 400 m. What standard of accuracy would it be reasonable for us to expect from the builders, who were a different culture in a different time, using different tools?

1.3 Pretty numbers

Certain combinations of π , φ and e produce numbers which round nicely to one or two decimals. These are listed in Table 2. Some of these are used in the discussions below.

Formula	“Full” value	Giza values using 1.618, 2.7183, 3.1416
$\frac{5\varphi e}{7\pi}$ or $\frac{5\pi}{6\varphi^2}$	1.000	1.000
$\frac{\pi}{\varphi^2}$	1.200	1.200
$\frac{\sqrt{\pi^2 + \varphi^2}}{e}$	1.300	1.300
$\frac{\varphi e}{\pi}$	1.400	1.400
$\frac{\pi \varphi}{e}$	1.870	1.870

Table 2: Pretty numbers

2 The site plan

Figure 2 shows the main original Giza site map, developed in *Zep Tepi Mathematics 101* [4], together with pyramid and space dimensions. I have adjusted the P6 size to 157 \mathcal{C} square, which is most likely the correct size. The star names associated with each pyramid are from *Zep Tepi Mathematics 101*, and the planet names from *The six pyramids and planets at Giza* [5].

Figure 2: Site plan with dimensions

Wikipedia's page on the Sphinx [6] gives the length as 73 metres, which is 139.42 \mathcal{C} , but Wikipedia rounds distances aggressively. A measurement I made (Figure 5) on Google Earth shows a length of 71.72 m which translates to 137 \mathcal{C} .

Figure 5: Sphinx length, 137 \mathcal{C}

Not many people have measured the Sphinx, unlike the Great Pyramid. The most well-known is probably Mark Lehner, for his 1991 dissertation *Archaeology of an Image: The Great Sphinx of Giza* [7]. I don't know if he took an approach like Piazza Smyth, who measured things one or twice, and took an average, or Petrie, who typically measured nine times over three days, then gave an average and error bounds. Given how many people have measured the Great Pyramid, getting mostly different results, it is difficult to rely on only one set of measurements, but that is all we have.

Lehner's focus was on the geology and history, so dimensions were probably not crucial. We quote the relevant text from his dissertation:

“The total length of the statue from the tip of the masonry-covered forepaw (which extends .26 m further east than the north forepaw) to the masonry-covered tail at the rump is 72.55 m. Assuming that the small, brick-sized masonry at the tip of the forepaws is no more than 0.15 m thick and that the masonry covering the tail is about 0.50 m thick (...), the length of the bedrock core is approximately 71.90 m. This would make the length of the bedrock reserved for the core body of the Sphinx about 137 Royal Cubits.”

“The Sphinx measures 19.10 m across the haunches, its widest part.”

“The total height of the statue, from its bedrock floor to the tip of the cobra on the forehead (as now preserved), is about 20.22 m, with some slight variation due to irregularities in the floor.”

I would argue that if the creators were able to carve the face, they were also able to carve the rest, and any brickwork is later restoration. I take the originally designed length as 137 \mathcal{C} . For the width, 19.1 m is 36.48 \mathcal{C} , and I take the original core width as 36 \mathcal{C} , as there is also masonry on the haunches.

The height is more challenging. The 20.22 m is 38.62 \mathcal{C} , but that includes cement work on the top. Ideally I would go with 38 \mathcal{C} , following the mantra that “dimensions and spaces between constructions are in whole cubits,” but there is a precedent for adopting a different value here. The King's Chamber height in the Great Pyramid is not an integer value, and the reason is purely to allow the mathematics that the designers incorporated, to work. See Figure 6 for an example. (*Observations on the King's Chamber Dimensions* [8]).

Figure 6: Khufu's chamber

So for the height, we will instead use 38.0556 \mathcal{C} , which is very precise and should be taken as a theoretical

ideal not necessarily achieved in practice.

As with the virtual “bounding rectangle” around the base, we now extend that to three dimensions and envisage a “bounding room” around the Sphinx. This virtual “bounding chamber” is 137 x 36 x 38.0556 G.

The bounding chamber has interesting mathematical properties. The first is that the area of the short face is 36×38.0556 , or 1370, which is ten times the length. This is the first reason why we feel 38.0556 is correct. It means that the volume of the bounding room is $10 \times 137 \times 137$, or 10 times the length squared.

We have seen this idea before. The volume of the coffer with lid in the Great Pyramid is equal to its length squared. (*Khufu’s Coffin* [9])

Figure 7: Khufu’s coffer

These dimensions are the real reasons for the unnatural feline dimensions, where the head is clearly too small for the body, and the body is too long.

4 How the Sphinx connects to the site plan

There are two key points on this bounding rectangle. The first and main one is the north-west corner, closest to Khufu, labelled SpNW in Figure 4. The second, less used, is the south west corner, SpSW.

The north west corner is calculated from Khufu, using the GPS co-ordinates provided by Wikipedia [10]. The point is 343 G east of the eastern edge of Khufu, and 806 G south of Khufu’s centre, as shown in Figure 8 on the OpenStreetMap extract, and Figure 9. Figure 8 shows it a little too far east, which may be due to the data which OpenStreetMaps uses to plot the Sphinx, the renovation brickwork, or even subtle differences in the GPS system at various times over the years. It is also possible that the builders may have made a measuring error.

Figure 8: The key point

Figure 9 shows the key point relative to Khufu and Khafre.

Figure 9: The key point

We now show why the values are 343 and 806 cubits.

4.1 The west-east position determined via φ

The Sphinx’s west-east position is determined using the golden ratio. The distance between P2 and P5 is π times the distance between P1 and P2. Similarly, the west-east distance from the eastern edge of Khufu to the west side of the Sphinx’s bounding rectangle, is φ times the distance between P1 and P2.

Figure 10: The golden ratio φ

$$\frac{666}{212} = 3.142 = \pi$$

$$\frac{343}{212} = 1.618 = \varphi$$

$$\frac{1077}{212} = 5.08 = 3.14 \times 1.618 = \pi\varphi$$

The numbers 212 and 343 are not part of the regular Fibonacci series, which is well-known for having the ratio between adjacent terms tend towards the golden ratio. They are, however, part of the Wythoff Array [11], shown in Table 3. The first row is the classic Fibonacci series.

4.2 The north-south position determined via ρ

The Sphinx’s north-south position is determined using the plastic ratio.

0	1	1	2	3	5	8	13	21	34	55	89	144
1	3	4	7	11	18	29	47	76	123	199	322	521
2	4	6	10	16	26	42	68	110	178	288	466	754
3	6	9	15	24	39	63	102	165	267	432	699	1131
4	8	12	20	32	52	84	136	220	356	576	932	1508
5	9	14	23	37	60	97	157	254	411	665	1076	1741
6	11	17	28	45	73	118	191	309	500	809	1309	2118
7	12	19	31	50	81	131	212	343	555	898	1453	2351
8	14	22	36	58	94	152	246	398	644	1042	1686	2728
9	16	25	41	66	107	173	280	453	733	1186	1919	3105
10	17	27	44	71	115	186	301	487	788	1275	2063	3338
11	19	30	49	79								
12	21	33	54	87								
13	22	35	57	92								

Table 3: The Wythoff Array and The Para-Fibonacci Sequence

Figure 11: The Plastic ratio ρ

The north-south distance from the centre of Khufu to the centre of Menkaure is 1414.5 G, as can be determined from Figure 2. This is almost $1000\sqrt{2}$, and indeed, the average of that, and the west-east distance between their outer edges, which is 1414 G, is an excellent approximation for $1000\sqrt{2}$.

The point SpNW divides the north-south line between the centres of Khufu and Menkaure in the plastic ratio.

$$\frac{806}{608.5} = 1.3246 = \rho \text{ (plastic ratio, 1.3247)}$$

Assorted other results appear as a consequence of the Sphinx’s location and dimensions. These are in Appendix A, so as to not distract from the main argument. These results include their usual favourite numbers, namely $\pi, \varphi, e, c, \alpha, \sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}, \sqrt{5}$ and the G.

5 Conclusion

The Sphinx, long an object of religious devotion and scientific speculation, at last gives up some of her secrets. Her location fits neatly into the existing irrational distance ratios in the Giza site plan. It is possible that the rest of the site is anchored to the north west corner of the bounding rectangle around the Sphinx.

Figure 12: Giza site design with the Sphinx

The Sphinx is offset from the main Giza site using the golden (ϕ) and plastic (ρ) ratios. These two numbers are the positive roots of two similar equations:

$$\text{Golden ratio : } \phi + 1 = \phi^2$$

$$\text{Plastic ratio : } \rho + 1 = \rho^3$$

This could be interpreted as the designer having fun, or a display of skill and knowledge.

The way that the P5 - P2 - Sphinx spaces give us $\pi : 1 : \phi$ (see Figure 12) is particularly elegant, seeing as these two irrationals were the most important to the designer.

These design choices are clearly not an accident. The designer knew exactly what she was doing.

We now need to decide if the Sphinx is entirely man-made, given that both Khufu and Khafre are built over hillocks. Their locations were determined by mathematical ratios, and based on an arrangement of the stars at the time of planning. There is also a school of thought that claims that the centre of Khufu was situated at 29.979167° north to match the speed of light in metres per second (299 792 458 m/s). Does this mean that the hillocks are also man-made, and that the entire Giza plateau has been considerably cut down to the current height?

6 Appendix A: Other results from the Sphinx location and size

The usual favourite constants, found in multiple places at Giza, are embedded in the design. Some are via distance ratios, others via simple arithmetic with actual cubit lengths. Some are revealed when you do conversions between rectangular and circular areas, or volumes.

π is the most frequent constant, as with the rest of Giza. The values used typically round to 3.14 or 3.142.

6.1 The speed of light c

The speed of light is one of the annoying numbers that pops up at Giza.

The speed of light at the time of construction was 572.55 M \mathcal{C} /s (*Khafre's pyramid elegantly encodes the speed of light* [12]). This number is hard-coded into the dimensions of both Khufu (Figure 13) and Khafre (Figure 14).

Figure 13: The speed of light in Khufu

The difference between Khufu's base circumcircle and incircle is $(440 \times 1.4142 \times 3.1416) - (440 \times 3.1416) = 572.55 \mathcal{C}$. This calculation also works in metres.

Figure 14: The speed of light in Khafre

In Khafre, the speed of light is given by $(100 \times (411 - 274))^{\frac{274}{411}} = 572.55 \mathcal{C}$. This calculation only works in cubits.

We note that 572.55 is a rather specific and particular number.

The Sphinx's location provides that number as well, albeit to only one decimal place.

Figure 15: The speed of light c

$$608.5 - 36 = 572.5 = c.$$

The proposed bounding room gives us the correct value.

The volume of the room is $137 \times 36 \times 38.0556 = 187690.2192$.

Treat that as a cube, then the side is $\sqrt[3]{187690.2192} = 57.255$, which is the exactly the same string of digits representing the speed of light as in Khufu and Khafre. The two pyramids give 572.55×10^6 G/s, while the Sphinx gives 57.255×10^7 G/s, with the scaling factor for the user to manage, as when using a slide rule.

This is the second reason why we propose that the design height was 38.0556 G.

6.2 Results related to φ

6.2.1 Inverse of φ^2

The area of the rectangle below Khufu, south to the level of the Sphinx, is equal to $\frac{1000000}{\varphi^2}$. The 1,000,000 is a scaling factor to move the decimal point.

Figure 16: The inverse of φ^2

$$\frac{1000000}{652 \times 586} = \frac{1000000}{382072} = 2.62 = \varphi^2 \text{ as best as can be done with the integer measurements.}$$

6.2.2 1000ϕ

Figure 17: 1000ϕ

$212 + 440 + 343 + 411 + 212 = 1618$ which is 1000ϕ .

6.3 Results related to π

6.3.1 $\sqrt{1000\pi}$

Figure 18: $\sqrt{1000\pi}$

$$\frac{\text{area of offset rectangle}}{\text{area bounding rectangle}} = \frac{343 \times 806}{137 \times 36} = 56.0539$$

Then $56.0539^2 = 3142 = 1000\pi$.

I was shown this during one of the many “final” proof-reading sessions. At the time I was doubting if my offsets and bounding rectangle dimensions were correct, since everything depends on them.

When I saw this result, I was stunned, and had a very emotional reaction ...literally “shock” and “awe.” The mind that could create this is beyond my understanding. It also acted as confirmation that my offsets and bounding rectangle were correct. It is the designer signing her work.

6.3.2 $10\pi^2$

The offset from Khafre, south to the level of the Sphinx, gives us $(10\pi)^2$.

Figure 19: $10\pi^2$

$$652 + 335 = 987 = 31.416^2 = (10\pi)^2$$

6.3.3 500π

The sum of the west-east spaces, from P4 to the Sphinx, plus its width, gives us 500π .

Figure 20: 500π

$$314 + 666 + 212 + 343 + 36 = 1571 = \frac{1000 \times 3.142}{2} = \frac{1000\pi}{2} = 500\pi$$

6.3.4 1000π

Figure 21: 1000φ

220 + 343 + 2236 + 343 = 3142 which is 1000π.

6.3.5 Inverses of π

The Sphinx's location and size lead to several references to π⁻¹. Since the inverse is often much smaller than 1, we scale it back to the familiar view by using an appropriate numerator instead of 1.

6.3.6 Length, breadth and height

$$\sqrt{\frac{100000}{\text{length} * (\text{width} + \text{height})}} = \sqrt{\frac{100000}{137 * (36 + 38.0556)}} = 3.14$$

6.3.7 P1 centre to SpSW

Figure 22: Diameter and circumference related to inverse of π

The distance for the centre of Khufu to the south-western corner of the Sphinx bounding rectangle, is given by

$$distance = \sqrt{(220 + 343)^2 + (806 + 36)^2} = 1012.9.$$

The square root of that is 31.826, and in turn $\frac{100}{31.826} = 3.142$.

So we can say that the distance is effectively $\left(\frac{100}{\pi}\right)^2$.

Then if that line was the diameter of a circle, the circumference would be $\pi\left(\frac{100}{\pi}\right)^2 = 3182.53$ and $\frac{10000}{3182.53} = 3.142$.

6.3.8 Area of bounding rectangle and π

Figure 23: Rectangle to π -based circle

The area of the bounding rectangle is $36 \times 137 = 4932$.

If that was a circle, the area would be given by $4932 = \pi r^2 = 3.14 \times 1570.7$

We note that $500 \times 3.1416 = 1570.8$, nearly the same as the r^2 .

The respective square roots, being the radii, are 39.632 and 39.633 cubits, a difference of less than 1 mm.

Thus the area of our bounding rectangle is effectively equal to the area of a circle with radius $\sqrt{\frac{1000\pi}{2}}$.

I have seen other similar calculations at Giza where they use slightly different values for π in the same formula. It may just be the way they did things.

6.3.9 Circle area leading to square related to π

Figure 24: Squaring the circle, cubits and metres

If we take the west-east offset from Khufu, which is 343 G, as the radius of a circle, then the area would be $343^2 \times 3.14 = 369417.86$.

A square with the same area would have a side of $\sqrt{369417.86} = 607.7975$ G.

In metres, that is 318.2428, or 318.25 to nearest quarter metre.

We note that $\frac{1000}{3.142} = 318.2686$, or 318.25 to nearest quarter metre.

So there is a curious relationship between the Sphinx's offset from Giza, and a length based on the inverse of π , but in metres.

6.3.10 Position relative to the double square also related to π

Figure 25: The position relative to the site double square

The SpNW point, relative to the outer double square around Giza, once again leads to π .

$$220 + 806 = 1026$$

$$2236 - 1026 = 1210$$

$$1026 * 1210 = 1241460$$

Treat this as the area of a circle. Then the radius = $\sqrt{\frac{1241460}{3.142}} = 628.58$, which is 200π (rounded) with π at 3.14.

6.3.11 π and $\sqrt{2}$

137 + 36 is 173, which is $100\sqrt{3}$, rounded.

The diagonal is $100\sqrt{2}$, or 141.65, as shown in §6.7.1.

Then the triangle of length, width and diagonal has a perimeter of $173 + 141.65 = 314.65$, which is approximately 100π .

The combination of 137 and 36 give best result for this calculation, within a range of a few cubits either side of those values.

Width	Length	$100\sqrt{2}$	$100\sqrt{3}$	100π	$\sqrt{2}$ error	$\sqrt{3}$ error	π error	Ave error
36	137	141.65	173	314.65	0.23	0	0.45	0.23
37	136	140.94	173	313.94	0.48	0	0.26	0.25
34	138	142.13	172	314.13	0.71	1	0.07	0.59
35	137	141.40	172	313.40	0.02	1	0.80	0.61
38	136	141.21	174	315.21	0.21	1	1.01	0.74

Table 4: $\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{3}, \pi$

6.3.12 Area of square and Sphinx

The main Giza site plan fits in a double square, with each square being $1000\sqrt{5}$, or 2236 € square. See Figures 2 and 21. Then the following calculation with the area of one square, and the base area of the Sphinx's bounding rectangle, again gives π .

$$\frac{100}{\sqrt{\frac{\text{area square}}{\text{area Sphinx}}}} = \frac{100}{\sqrt{\frac{2236^2}{137 \times 36}}} = 3.14$$

6.4 Results related to Euler’s number

The dimensions between Khafre and the Sphinx give us Euler’s number, correct to two decimals.

Figure 26: Euler’s number e

$$\frac{212 \times 440}{343} = 272 = 100e$$

$$\frac{212 + 440}{343 + 137} = \frac{652}{480} = 1.36 = \frac{2.72}{2} = \frac{e}{2}$$

6.4.1 $e - 1$

The value $e - 1$ is the ratio between the \mathbb{G} and the foot, as $\frac{52.36}{1.7183} = 30.472$.

We find this value, times 1000, by using the distance between P4 and P5, which is 314 \mathbb{G} , and the distance between Khufu and the Sphinx, which is 343 \mathbb{G} . Then

$314 \times 343 = 107702$. Convert that to metres squared:

$107702 \times 0.5236^2 = 29527.25291$. Then the square root of that is 171.83, which is $100(e - 1)$.

6.5 Results related to the cubit : metre ratio

The cubit : metre ratio is embedded in the Sphinx’s location relative to Khufu and Khafre.

Figure 27: The cubit : metre ratio

$343 \times 335 = 114905$. A square with the same area would have a side of $\sqrt{114905} = 338.9764$.

The diagonal of that square is $338.9764 \times \sqrt{2} = 338.9764 \times 1.4142 = 479.3804$.

Then $\frac{251}{479.3804} = 0.5236$ which is the length of the \mathbb{G} in metres. Or $251 : 479.3804 = \mathbb{G} : \text{m}$.

6.6 Results related to 137, the inverse of the Fine Structure Constant α

The original Sphinx was 137 G long. 137 is **the** most annoying [13] number we find at Giza, due to its role as the approximate inverse of the Fine Structure Constant α .

137 is also the divisor in Khafre (Figure 14), located behind the Sphinx. Khafre's base is $137 \times 3 = 411$, and height is $137 \times 2 = 274$. So 137 is a link between the Sphinx and Khafre's pyramid.

6.7 Results related to Square roots

The Sphinx's dimensions and offsets from Khafre and Khufu give us the favoured square roots, $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{3}$, and $\sqrt{5}$. The first two are rough approximations, while $\sqrt{5}$ is quite good.

6.7.1 Root 2

Figure 28: $\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{3}$

The diagonal of the bounding rectangle is given by $\sqrt{137^2 + 36^2} = 141.65$. Then the square of one hundredth of that is $1.4165^2 = 2.00647 = 2$.

6.7.2 Root 3

$137 + 36 = 173$. Then the square of one hundredth of that is $1.73^2 = 2.9929 = 3$.

6.7.3 Root 5

The product of the offsets from Khafre and Khufu give us $\sqrt{5}$.

Figure 29: $\sqrt{5}$

$652 \times 343 = 223636$, Then the square of one hundred-thousandth of that is $2.23636^2 = 5.0013 = 5$.

6.8 The Sphinx and the Great Pyramid

Figure 30: Khufu's Kepler design

The Sphinx length plus width is $137 + 36 = 173$. This slots perfectly into a series with Khufu's design, which is based on the Kepler Triangle.

$$173 : 220 : 280 : 356 :: \frac{1}{\sqrt{\varphi}} : 1 : \sqrt{\varphi} : \varphi$$

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